

The Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation: Kinetic Energy ($\frac{1}{2}mv^2$), Potential Energy (mgh), and Work done (mas)

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Abstract: The Einstein's mass-energy equation is equal to the sum of rest mass energy and kinetic energy. This paper discusses the sum of kinetic energy and potential energy or the sum of kinetic energy and work done that relates to the Einstein's mass-energy equation.

Keywords: equations of motion, rest mass energy, relativity

Potential Energy = Kinetic Energy

Now, let us prove that the potential energy is equal to the kinetic energy of a freely falling object with non-zero mass (m), velocity (v), and gravitational acceleration (g) at a specific point, where h is the height from the specific point to the ground.

The equations of motion including potential and kinetic energy are given below:

Kinetic energy (K) = $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and potential energy (P) = mgh .

Let us prove that $P = K$.

$$P = mgh. \quad (1)$$

$$s = ut + \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow s = 0 + \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow s = \frac{1}{2}gt^2. \quad (2)$$

$$v^2 = u^2 + 2gh \Rightarrow v^2 = 0 + 2gh \Rightarrow v^2 = 2g\left(\frac{1}{2}gt^2\right) \Rightarrow v^2 = g^2t^2. \quad (3)$$

By substituting the equation (2) in the equation (1), we get

$$P = mg \times h \Rightarrow P = mg \times \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow P = \frac{1}{2}mg^2t^2. \quad (4)$$

By substituting the equation (3) in the equation (4), we conclude that

$$P = \frac{1}{2}mg^2t^2 \Rightarrow P = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = K. \quad (5)$$

Hence, it is proved that the potential energy is equal to the kinetic energy of the object.

Work done = Kinetic Energy

Work done (W) by a force on an object is equal to the magnitude of the force (F) multiplied by the displacement (s) of the object, i.e. $W = F \times s = mas$, where $F = ma$. Also, the kinetic energy (K) is equal to its work done (W), i.e. $K = W$.

The kinetic energy (K) of a moving object with velocity (v) and mass (m) = $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$.

Let us prove that $W=K$.

$$W = F \times s = ma \times s. \quad (6)$$

$$s = ut + \frac{1}{2}at^2 \Rightarrow s = 0 + \frac{1}{2}at^2 \Rightarrow s = \frac{1}{2}at^2. \quad (7)$$

$$v^2 = u^2 + 2as \Rightarrow v^2 = 0 + 2as \Rightarrow v^2 = 2a\left(\frac{1}{2}at^2\right) \Rightarrow v^2 = a^2t^2. \quad (8)$$

By substituting the equation (7) in the equation (6), we get

$$W = ma \times s \Rightarrow W = ma \times \frac{1}{2}at^2 \Rightarrow W = \frac{1}{2}ma^2t^2. \quad (9)$$

By substituting the equation (8) in the equation (9), we conclude that

$$W = \frac{1}{2}ma^2t^2 \Rightarrow W = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = K. \quad (10)$$

Hence, it is proved that the work done is equal to the kinetic energy.

The Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation

Now, let show that the sum of kinetic energy and potential energy or the sum of kinetic energy and work done relates to the Einstein's mass-energy equation.

$$\text{Total energy } (E) = K + P = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = 2\left(\frac{1}{2}mv^2\right) = mv^2 \quad (OR)$$

$$\text{Total energy } (E) = K + W = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = 2\left(\frac{1}{2}mv^2\right) = mv^2.$$

If we consider that the velocity (v) of an object is equal to the speed of light (c), then $E = mc^2$. But, the velocity (v) of any object with non-zero mass is less than the speed of light.

Therefore, $E = mc_v^2$, where $c_v < c$.

If there is a value c_u such that $c_u < c$, then $c_u \leq c_v < c$.

Hence, $E \neq mc^2$.

In addition, the following references [1-17] give more information regarding the energy of an object in motion.

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